

Image-Based Volume Estimation for Food in a Bowl

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Abstract: Image-assisted dietary assessment has become popular in dietary monitoring studies in recent years. However, food volume estimation is still a challenging problem due to the lack of 3D information in a 2D image and the occlusion of the food by itself or container (e.g., bowl, cup). This study aims to investigate the relationship between the observable surface of food in a bowl and a normalized index (i.e., bowl fullness) to represent its volume. A mathematical model is established for describing different shapes of bowls, and a convenient experimental method is proposed to determine the bowl shape. An image feature called Food Area Ratio (FAR) is used to estimate the volume of food in a bowl based on the relationship between bowl fullness and the FAR calculated from the image. Both simulations and experiments with real food/liquid demonstrate the feasibility and accuracy of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Food volume estimation, Bowl shape, Image-assisted dietary assessment

1. Introduction

It is estimated that six out of ten US adults have at least one chronic disease (e.g., heart disease, diabetes), while four out of ten have two or more [1]. Care of chronic diseases consumes more than 90% of the annual health care expenditures in the US [2]. Poor-quality diet is thought to be one of the leading risk factors causing these diseases [3]. Although consistent evidence demonstrates that a balanced, healthy diet can help prevent, delay, and manage these diseases [4], changing eating habits is a process hard for most people to adopt. In addition to educational intervention to promote healthy diet and weight loss, conducting a thorough dietary assessment allows dietitians to identify both composition and energy contents in a person's diet, thus helping individuals change their dietary behavior. However, traditional dietary assessment tools are based on self-report, which may be inaccurate and prone to subjective bias [5,6].

In recent years, as information and mobile technologies advance, image-based dietary assessment tools have emerged which provide objective and comprehensive dietary data without relying on self-report [7-23]. Food images are captured either by a smartphone or a wearable device. Then the images are analyzed to recognize foods, estimate their volumes, and evaluate calorie/nutrient contents using computer algorithms with or without assistance from a nutritionist/researcher. As the artificial intelligence (AI) technology is introduced to the field of nutrition and dietetics, the accuracy of automatic food recognition has increased dramatically [16-26]. However, food volume estimation from an image is still a very challenging problem primarily due to 1) lack of a scale reference to determine the size of the food, 2) lack of 3D information from a single view of the food, and 3) invisible part of the food due to occlusion of the food itself or the container. To obtain a scale reference in an image, a physical object with known size, such as a checkerboard, a coin, or a pair of chopsticks is often placed

intentionally beside the food [27-32]. Once an image is taken, a scale factor (i.e., the physical area represented by a pixel) is calculated from the number of pixels covered by the scale reference object in the image. When the food item is located on the same plane as the reference object or close to the object, its area can be estimated from the scale factor by counting the number of pixels it covers. Because the scale factor is spatially different at different locations of the image due to the variation in the view angle of the camera, the 3D location corresponding to each food pixel in the image must be known. From the observed distortion of the scale reference in the image, the projection between the food plane (which is usually the plane of the reference, e.g., tabletop) in the 3D physical space and the plane of the 2D image can be determined. Then, the 3D physical space occupied by food is estimated from the number of image pixels representing the height/length/diameter of the food when a regular shape can be used to model the food [33-35].

Besides using a scale reference, depth images (e.g., those obtained using a depth sensor) and stereo images have been used to obtain 3D information [36-44]. However, most smartphones are not yet equipped with depth cameras. Although modern smartphones are equipped with multiple cameras, these cameras are located next to each other within the backside of the smartphone. The limited camera separation results in limited accuracy in depth perception, which seriously affects the accuracy of food volume estimation. Therefore depth/stereo images are currently obtained by bulky depth sensors (e.g., Intel RealSense RGBD sensor [41,44,45]), which are not convenient for practical use. In addition, to tackle the occlusion problem, multiple images taken from different views of the food are required [13,17,21,46]. Because of the significant burden to acquire such images, this approach is usually not implemented in the field of dietary assessment. A common solution is to assign a shape template or wireframe model (e.g., a sphere for an orange, a wedge for a piece of pizza) to fit the shape of the food

in the image [34,42,47-51], but manual fitting is usually required. Recently, deep neural networks have been used to reconstruct 3D food with the help of depth image [52-55]. To implement deep neural networks, a large number of training images are required. However, few datasets of food images include volume information since generating such images (especially for foods with irregular shapes) involves complex procedures of food volume measurements (e.g., water or seed displacement [47,50,56] or 3D reconstruction from depth images [41,45,46]). Most of the current available datasets are obtained in well-controlled experimental environments (e.g., fixed food containers, limited food types) [41,45,46].

Because it is convenient to take food images with a smartphone or a wearable device for the participants in dietary studies, our work focuses on estimating food volume from a single-view image. As placing a scale reference (e.g., a specially designed checkerboard) beside the food is usually unwelcome by participants, a food container (a plate or a bowl) has been used as the scale reference [28,47,57]. However, estimating the volume of the food contained in a bowl is a more challenging problem since, in this case, the food volume in the bowl may be a combination of two parts. The bottom part is determined by the size/shape of the bowl, while the top part, if present, is free-standing with random shape (depending on the physical properties of the food). To characterize the bowl size, Raju et. al. used a range sensor to measure the distance between the camera and the bowl when the food image was taken, then estimated its diameter and height [58]. However, the camera's orientation must be known. In their experiment, the pitch angle of the range sensor was measured manually with a protractor which is not practical in dietary studies. Akpa et. al. proposed to use a pair of chopsticks with known-length as scale references to measure the dimensions of a bowl and the volume of food in it simultaneously [28,59]. One chopstick was placed on top of the bowl, and the other on the table.

Then, a top-view image (i.e., the camera's line of sight coincides with the central axis of the bowl) was taken. The bowl's diameter and depth were obtained by analyzing the lengths (in pixels) of the two chopsticks and the diameter of the bowl in the image. Similarly, the diameter and height of the food in the bowl were estimated after the food area was segmented from the image. The volume of the food was then calculated assuming the bowl shape was a spherical cap. However, this assumption is not accurate since the diameter and height alone cannot fully determine the actual shape of the bowl [49]. In addition, for food without a flat surface, the actual height of the food cannot be identified easily from a top-view image. To estimate the actual shape/size of a bowl, Jia et. al. proposed to pre-measure the bowls used in dietary studies. For each bowl, an adhesive paper ruler was centrally taped across its bottom and then a top-view image of the bowl was taken [57]. An optimization algorithm was used to reconstruct the bowl in 3D by analyzing the distortion of the equally spaced markers on the ruler. This approach provides a simple way to determine bowl shape and volume experimentally, but the algorithm is relatively complex.

In this work, we present a different approach to recover the scale factor and reconstruct the bowl. A mathematical model is established for describing different shapes of bowls. Instead of taping the bowl with a paper ruler and then imaging [57], a different experimental method is implemented to determine the parameters of the bowl model. We also present an approach to estimate the volume of food in a bowl based on an image feature called Food Area Ratio (FAR). To improve food volume estimation accuracy, a quantity called "bowl fullness" is defined which describes how full a bowl is rather than how much food is in the bowl. Then, we investigate the relationship between the bowl fullness of food and the FAR based on the proposed bowl model. Finally, the food volume is obtained by multiplying the fullness value and the volume of the bowl. Our approaches are evaluated using

both computer simulation and actual bowls with foods. Satisfactory results are obtained from the evaluation experiments.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the mathematical model to represent bowl shape and methods to estimate volume of food in a bowl. Section 3 details the experiments using the proposed methods. Section 4 discusses practical issues when the methods are used in practical dietary studies. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. Methods

To estimate food volume in a bowl from a single image, the following steps are implemented: 1) modeling the shape of a bowl mathematically; 2) deriving the relationship between the observable area of the food and its volume; and 3) estimating food volume using the concept of bowl fullness. These steps are detailed in the following subsections.

2.1 Mathematical model of a bowl

A spherical cap (i.e., a section of a sphere cutoff by a plane) has been used to model the bowl [28,49]. In this model, the bowls that have the same radii and heights are assumed to have the same spherical surface. These assumptions represent a serious limitation because bowls could be “plump” or “skinny” in shape. To remove this limitation, we propose a new model expressed mathematically by

$$z = H \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{R} \right)^q, \quad \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \leq R, \quad q > 1, \quad (1)$$

where x, y, z are coordinates in 3D space, H is the height of the bowl ($H > 0$), R is its radius, and parameter q controls its shape [60]. A plot of the model is shown in Fig. 1a. To better understand the effect of q , we illustrate the cross-section of interior surfaces of five bowls in the x - z plane (Fig. 1b).

These bowls have the same R and H , but different q . It can be seen that the bowl with larger q is “plumper”. To quantify the bowl shape analytically, we define an index called bowl plumpness [60], denoted by P , as

$$P = \frac{V_{\text{Bowl}}}{V_{\text{Cylinder}}}, \quad (2)$$

where V_{Bowl} and V_{Cylinder} represent, respectively, the volumes of the bowl and the cylinder with the same radius and height. Based on Eq. (1), it can be derived (details in the Appendix) that V_{Bowl} is given by

$$V_{\text{Bowl}} = \frac{q}{q+2} \pi R^2 H. \quad (3)$$

Since V_{Cylinder} equals $\pi R^2 H$, we have

$$P = \frac{q}{q+2}. \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) indicates that the plumpness of the bowl depends solely on q .

The estimation of food volume requires the use of a physical unit, such as milliliter, or measurement cup. Previous studies have shown that it is not straightforward for a human to estimate food volume from an image in terms of a physical unit [57,61,62]. To avoid this cognitive challenge, we proposed to use the “bowl fullness”, a unitless quantity, that normalizes the volume of food in a bowl [57,60], defined as

$$F = \frac{V_{\text{Food}}}{V_{\text{Bowl}}} \times 100\%. \quad (5)$$

If the food is in a liquid form and the radius of the flat food surface is r (Fig. 1c), the bowl fullness takes a simple form:

$$F = \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{q+2}. \quad (6)$$

The derivation of Eq. (6) is provided in the Appendix. Clearly, the food volume can be calculated easily as the product of F and the bowl volume according to Eq. (5).

2.2 Food Area Ratio (FAR) in food image

It is well-known that the projection of a circle in the 3D physical space onto a plane is a circle, an ellipse, or a straight line, depending on the orientation and location of the camera. In our study, the circle is considered as a special ellipse, and the case of a straight line is ignored because it corresponds to the view angle of the camera (defined as the angle between the optical axis of the camera and the top surface of the bowl) being zero, which is almost impossible. Thus, we assume that the projections of the bowl rim (radius = R) and the circular food boundary (radius = r) onto the camera's image plane are ellipses (shown in Fig. 2a in red and blue, respectively). The equations of these two ellipses, denoted as $Ellipse_R$ and $Ellipse_r$, are written as

$$\begin{cases} x^2 + b_R xy + c_R y^2 + d_R x + e_R y + f_R = 0, \\ x^2 + b_r xy + c_r y^2 + d_r x + e_r y + f_r = 0, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where x and y are the variables in the x - y plane, and $b_R, c_R, d_R, e_R, f_R, b_r, c_r, d_r, e_r,$ and f_r are parameters that determine the two ellipses. The visible food surface is the intersection of the two ellipses, i.e., $area(Ellipse_R \cap Ellipse_r)$ (the cyan region in Fig. 2a). In this case, the Food Area Ratio (FAR) is the ratio between the area of the visible food surface and the area enclosed by the bowl rim (i.e., red ellipse in Fig. 2a).

$$FAR = \frac{area(Ellipse_R \cap Ellipse_r)}{area(Ellipse_R)}. \quad (8)$$

Since the coefficients in Eq. (7) are determined by the camera's extrinsic parameters (camera location and orientation) and intrinsic parameters (such as focal length, pixel size, etc., usually provided by the camera manufacture or obtained via camera calibration), FAR can be written as a function of $r, R,$ and camera parameters:

$$FAR = \varphi(r, R, camera\ parameters). \quad (9)$$

Since Eq. (6) can be rewritten as

$$r = RF^{\frac{1}{q+2}}, \quad (10)$$

when substituting Eq. (10) into Eq. (9), FAR can be represented alternatively as

$$\text{FAR} = \psi(F, R, \text{camera parameters}). \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) indicates that, if R and camera parameters are known, the relationship between FAR and bowl fullness F can be determined by $\psi(\cdot)$.

However, $\psi(\cdot)$ is a very complex function, not easily expressed analytically. We propose a numerical method to approximate this function for each bowl image as follows. First, a sequence of hypothetical flat surface levels in the 3D virtual bowl (assuming that the bowl contains a liquid) is simulated to represent increments of the liquid volumes, e.g., 10% of the bowl volume, shown in Fig. 2b. Then, the boundary of each surface level is projected according to the provided camera parameters (Fig. 2c). The camera parameters can be determined by the projection of the bowl rim (details in Section 2.4). Next, the FAR value corresponding to each level is calculated and shown as a red asterisk in Fig. 2d. The highest level represents the rim of the bowl. Finally, the cubic spline interpolation is applied to the discrete values (red asterisks) resulting in a smooth curve (blue curve in Fig. 2d). It appears from the plot of the curve that the FAR monotonically increases with the bowl fullness F . In fact, this observed monotonicity is generally true. To verify, we only need to prove that the FAR increases with r because Eq. (10) indicates that r is monotonically increasing with F . As shown in Fig. 2e, the green $Ellipse_{r_1}$ and blue $Ellipse_{r_2}$ represent the ellipses corresponding to flat surfaces with radius r_1 and r_2 ($r_2 > r_1$), respectively. The intersected $area(Ellipse_R \cap Ellipse_{r_2})$ cannot be smaller than or equal to $area(Ellipse_R \cap Ellipse_{r_1})$ as the latter (pink region) is included in the interior of the former. Thus, the FAR corresponds to a larger r is also larger.

2.3 Measurement of bowl parameters

Before an image-based dietary study, the bowls to be used in the study are pre-measured and their models are pre-established. Previously, we reported a method using an adhesive paper ruler to obtain bowl parameters [57,60]. This paper ruler is centrally taped across the bottom of a bowl. Then, an image of the bowl is taken with a phone. Since the equally spaced markers on the ruler are distorted when observed from the image, analyzing the distortion allows us to reconstruct the shape of the bowl in 3D. Although the bowl taping procedure is simple, the algorithm involves coordinate transformation and numerical optimization which are relatively complex. In this work, we present a different method with both procedural and computational simplicity. First, we measure both the diameter and the depth of the bowl with a ruler. Then, we measure the volume of the bowl by weighing (using a digital scale) or measuring (using a graduated cylinder) the water that fills up the bowl. With the measured bowl volume V_{Bowl} , depth H , and rim radius R , Eq. (2) is evaluated to obtain bowl plumpness P . Finally, parameter q is calculated by rewriting Eq. (4):

$$q = \frac{2P}{1-P}. \quad (12)$$

2.4 Food volume estimation

With the preconstructed bowl model, the volume of food in the bowl (exemplified in Fig. 3a) is estimated according to the following steps: 1) segmenting both the boundary of the food surface and the rim of the bowl in the image; 2) calculating the FAR for the food in this image, which is defined as the ratio between the food area and the area of the bowl rim (Fig. 3b); 3) estimating the camera extrinsic parameters (i.e., the position and orientation of the camera) based on the rim of the bowl using our algorithm previously reported in [33,47]; 4) simulating the relationship between FAR and

the food volume inside this bowl as described in Section 2.2 (Fig. 3c); and 5) finding the estimated bowl fullness corresponding to the calculated FAR of the food (horizontal value of the blue asterisk in Fig. 3c) in the image from the simulated FAR- F curve. The food volume is estimated by multiplying the estimated fullness (vertical value of the blue asterisk) with the bowl volume.

In the previous derivation, the food surface in a bowl is assumed to be flat or nearly flat. However, the food surface is often bumpy with a peak at or close to the middle region [49]. Since the exact information about the 3D surface is unattainable from a 2D image, we propose a cone model in which the food in a bowl is modeled as the sum of two parts separated by a flat surface in the bowl (Fig. 4a). The bottom part is the portion of food under this surface for which the volume is determined by the shape of the bowl. The top part is modeled as a cone with a flat surface as its base. The vertex of the cone is approximated as the intersected point (the red asterisk in Fig. 4b) of the food boundary and the projection of the central axis (z -axis in Fig. 1) of the virtual 3D bowl (shown in Fig. 4b as the green line). To find the best match between the cone model and the food boundary, the bowl volume is divided between 1% and 100% with increments of 1%. In each division, a contour matching score, called Intersection Over Union (IoU), is computed. The IoU is a widely used evaluation metric in image segmentation tasks. In our case, it measures the overlap between the visible food area and the cone model, a higher value indicating a better match. The best base is determined as the one with the highest score (Fig. 4c). The volume of the top cone is calculated using its height and base, and the volume under the base is determined by the bowl shape which can be computed according to Eq. (6).

3. Experimental Results

3.1. Simulation Study

Three bowl models were chosen to represent bowls of different shapes (Fig. 5). A series of simulations were conducted to 1) build each bowl virtually in 3D, 2) project the hypothetical surface levels (representing different volumes) to an image, and 3) investigate the relationship between FAR and food volume. In this study, an ideal pin-hole camera model was used to project the virtual 3D bowl on a 2D image [63].

For each bowl model, the number of surface levels was first set to 50, corresponding to the bowl fullness from 2% to 100% with a 2% increment. The highest level (fullness = 100%) corresponds to the boundary of the bowl. Then, the 50 surface levels were projected to an image for an assumed camera location and orientation. Next, FAR corresponding to each level was calculated and plotted as 50 dots in Fig. 6. The three columns in Fig. 6 correspond to the three bowl models in Fig. 5. The top row shows the simulation results when the camera positions are fixed while the view angle changes from 10° to 80° with an interval of 10° . The bottom row shows 20 simulation results when the camera locations and orientations are random. When the view angle is small (e.g., the top curve in Figs. 6a and 6c), the food cannot be observed unless the fullness is large enough, so the FAR is zero before the food is observable. It can also be noticed that the FAR is not zero even when the fullness is very small (e.g., the bottom curve in Figs. 6a-f), which may be caused by the flat bottom of the bowl. Even a thin layer of food (e.g., bowl fullness = 2%) has a relative large food surface area in the bowl when the view angle is large, leading to a FAR much larger than zero.

3.2. Experiments with actual bowls

3.2.1. Estimation of the shape model for each bowl

Two experiments were conducted in this study. Three bowls were used in Experiment 1 and one bowl in Experiment 2. For each bowl, its diameter, height, and capacity were measured, and parameter q was estimated. Details of these procedures have been described in Section 2.3. The shape models for all the four bowls are shown in Fig. 7.

3.2.2. Experiment 1

The aim of this experiment is to verify the relationship derived in Section 2.2. In this experiment, the position and orientation of the smartphone (pixel size 1.22 μm , focal length 2.9 mm) were fixed, facing toward the bowl on top of a kitchen weighing scale. Each time, a small portion of black tea (between 10 g to 50 g) was filled in the bowl and an image was taken after each filling. Three images of bowl #1 (out of 11 images) are shown in Fig. 8. The FAR- F curve was simulated following Section 2.2 using its bowl model, shown as the blue curve in Fig. 9a. For each image, the ground truth of the fullness value was calculated as the ratio between the weight of the tea (i.e., the volume of the tea) and the bowl volume. The actual FAR was calculated by the ratio between the segmented area of the tea and the area of the bowl rim. Each red asterisk in Fig. 9a represents the actual FAR- F for each image. Similar results for bowl #2 and #3 are shown in Figs. 9b and 9c, respectively.

It can be observed that, although the experimental results roughly match the simulated curves, errors are apparent and, for some bowls, the errors tend to have some biases (e.g., the deviation between the red asterisk and the blue curve shown in Figs. 9b and 9c). These errors and biases may be caused by 1) mismatch of the actual bowl and the bowl model, 2) inaccuracy of the rim detection due to the thickness of the bowl and lack of a sharp edge at the rim, and 3) inaccuracy in the segmentation of the tea due primarily to the half-transparency of the black tea. Our study indicates that, although carefulness and experience in measurements helped to improve the accuracy, certain sources of errors are not avoidable in field dietary studies (detailed in Discussion Section). When the simulated FAR- F curves were used to estimate the fullness of tea in each image following the procedure in Section 2.4, the maximum absolute errors for the three bowls were 2.5%, 7.5%, and 8.4%, respectively. Detailed results are shown in Fig. 10.

3.2.3. Experiment 2

In this experiment, six Asian foods were purchased from cafeterias. The ingredients of these foods include lotus root, bitter melon, green bean, beancurd sheet, winter melon, and water bamboo. The

cooking method was either stir-fried or braised. For each food, four different portions of the food were placed in Bowl #4, and 4-6 images were taken by a researcher with a smartphone. A total of 135 images were analyzed in this study. These images were taken using two different smartphones from different view angles and locations. The phones used were iPhone 6 (pixel size 1.22 μm , focal length 4.2 mm) and Xiaomi (pixel size 1.4 μm , focal length 4.2 mm). The view angles varied from 36.5° to 68.9°, and food-to-camera distances were in the range of 125 mm and 342 mm, calculated using the algorithm in [33,47]. Examples of the food images are shown in Fig. 11. The ground truth of the food volume was measured using a density-based approach described in [33,57]. The food volume in the bowl that appeared in each image was estimated after the rim of the bowl was detected and the food region within the bowl was segmented using the MATLAB Image Processing Toolbox [64].

Because the shape of food surface cannot be determined accurately from a 2D image, we calculated the matching score (i.e., IoU) between the segmented food and the hypothetical flat surfaces corresponding to different levels of food volume (from 1% to 100% with 1% increment). If there was at least one score exceeding a pre-set threshold (0.85), this food was assumed to have a flat surface. However, when the camera's view angle is large as shown in Figs. 3a and 11b, the top part of the food cannot be observed from the food boundary, thus the food volume cannot be estimated using the cone model even if the food surface is not flat. Therefore, in our study, if the view angle was larger than 50°, the *FAR approach* was used. Otherwise, the fullness of food was estimated using either the *FAR approach* or the *cone model approach* (in Section 2.4) based on whether the food surface was flat. The estimated results of bowl fullness are listed in Fig. 12. The median and the interquartile range (IQR) of the fullness errors over all 135 images are -8.8% and 14.7% (equivalent to -54.3 cm^3 and 91.4 cm^3), respectively.

We noticed that most Asian foods in a bowl do not have a flat surface even though the contour matching score is high, as shown in Figs. 11a, 11b, and 13. For those images, the bowl fullness of food estimated using the FAR method does not count the top part, so the estimation results are usually smaller (Fig. 14). If the cone model is used for these cases, the current method to determine food height is also not accurate, leading to a larger estimation (in Fig. 14). Thus, we proposed a *combined approach* to average the estimation results of the two methods to compromise the two estimates. In our study, we also noticed that the height of the food can be determined more precisely by manually clicking the position of peak (shown in Fig. 13). If manual selected height is used, the *cone model approach* is called *manual approach*. A comparison between these approaches for all the images of root lotus is illustrated in Fig. 14. The boxplot results of fullness errors using the combined and manual approaches for all the images are shown in Fig. 15. The median and the interquartile range (IQR) of the fullness errors are 0.9% and 10.6% (equivalent to 5.5 cm³ and 65.6 cm³) for the manual approach, and -1.8% and 11.7% (equivalent to -10.9 cm³ and 72.3 cm³) for the combined approach. Both are significantly better than the original approach.

4. Discussions

This study demonstrates that the volume of food in a bowl can be estimated from a single image accurately when the bowl is pre-measured. However, there are several limitations and concerns when this approach is used in a field dietary study.

One obvious limitation is that the volume of food in a bowl cannot be estimated if the food cannot be seen in the image. This happens when the amount of food and/or the view angle is too small. When the food picture is taken using a smartphone, this situation can be voided by manually adjusting the view angle. It should be noted that the view angle cannot be set too large if the food surface is not flat. Otherwise, the shape information about the top part of the food could be located inside the food

boundary. We recommend the view angle to be adjusted in the neighborhood of 45° and, if necessary, increased to avoid a severe occlusion. If a wearable device is used to acquire food images, a loss or occlusion of food view may still occur since the location of the device is relatively fixed on the body. However, if the view angle of the wearable device is adjustable [65], the occlusion can be minimized. In addition, if multiple foods are contained in a single plate or bowl, the volume of each food needs to be estimated individually. Although this problem is not addressed by this manuscript, in practice, people do not place multiple foods within a single bowl as often as placing them on a single plate.

The mismatch between the mathematical bowl model and the actual bowl is another limitation. Not all the dining bowls can be represented accurately by the model. For those odd-shaped bowls, if the longitudinal section of the bowl can be represented as a single-valued function, e.g., using the method in [57], the relationship between the FAR and the food volume can still be simulated since the volume under the visible surface is known. Thus, the proposed method is still applicable. As the calculation of FAR depends on the detected boundaries of food and bowl, the inaccuracy in the boundary detection is another source of the estimation error. With the advance of AI technology, a novel food segmentation algorithm reported in [66] is expected to increase the accuracy.

In dietary studies, when the bowl is not placed on a horizontal plane or is held in a hand, the simulated flat surface of hypothetical liquid will not match the actual surface of a liquid or a self-flattening food. Thus, it is best to check that the dining table is level or nearly level before a dietary study and adjust if necessary. If food images are already acquired from an inclined surface, the *FAR approach* is recommended to calculate the fullness instead of searching for the best matched surface [57].

To conduct a dietary study without using a scale reference, all plates and bowls that may appear in food images need to be premeasured. For shallow plates, usually a measure of plate diameter is sufficient. For deep plates, the measurement method for bowls is applicable. Since an identification of the bowl/plate in the image is necessary, misidentification could be a problem when too many types of bowls and plates are used. Therefore, it will be convenient if food containers used in the

study are standardized, as those used in a school or hospital cafeteria [44]. Using disposal plates/bowls of standard sizes can be another option.

For real food, the assumption of a flat food surface is accurate for beverages, soups and other self-flattening foods. Therefore, in most cases, rather than identifying from the image, whether the food surface is flat can also be determined from the name or properties of the food. Although the manual surface peak selection method provides better estimation for food without a flat surface, it increases the burden for image processing. Texture analysis or deep learning of the food images may provide a better characterization of the food surface in the future.

5. Conclusions

We have demonstrated that, for an image containing food in a premeasured bowl, the bowl itself can be used as a powerful reference for estimating food volume. A mathematical model containing three parameters is proposed to fully characterize both the size and the shape of the bowl. Based on this model, a new experimental method is developed to obtain model parameters using a ruler and a weighing scale. Once a food image is obtained, the mathematical relationship between the observable food surface in the image and the food volume is simulated, and the volume of food is estimated based on the simulated relationship. We have studied the cases of volume estimation for food with and without a flat surface in a bowl. Our experiments have demonstrated the effectiveness of our methods.

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Appendix:

Because of the symmetry of the proposed bowl model in Eq. (1), the virtual bowl in Fig. 1a can be formed by rotating the curve in Eq. (A1) (shown in Fig. 1c) around z axis by 360° .

$$z = H \left(\frac{x}{R} \right)^q \quad (\text{A1})$$

For a bowl whose shape can be represented as Eq. (A1), if the radius of the food surface is assumed to be r (Fig. 1c), the volume of food underneath this surface can be represented as

$$V_{\text{Food}} = \int_0^h \pi x^2 dz = \int_0^r \pi x^2 H R^{-q} q x^{q-1} dx = \int_0^r q \pi H R^{-q} x^{q+1} dx = \frac{q}{q+2} \pi R^2 H \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^{q+2} \quad (\text{A2})$$

where h is the height of the food surface.

When $r = R$, the volume of food equals to the volume of the bowl. So

$$V_{\text{Bowl}} = \frac{q}{q+2} \pi R^2 H. \quad (\text{A3})$$

Combining Eqs. (5), (A2) and (A3), bowl fullness of the food with surface radius r can be calculated

by

$$F = \frac{\frac{q}{q+2} \pi R^2 H \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^{q+2}}{\frac{q}{q+2} \pi R^2 H} = \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^{q+2}. \quad (\text{A4})$$

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Figure 1. (a) Virtual 3D bowl surface. (b) Cross-section of five bowl surfaces in x - z plane showing the effect of q on the shape of the bowl. (c) Bowl model with radius R and height H , and a flat food surface with radius r and height h .

Figure 2. (a) Projected ellipses corresponding to the rim of the bowl (red ellipse) and the flat food surface (blue ellipse). (b) Simulated volumetric levels (blue ellipses) where each level represents a 10% increment of the bowl volume. (c) Projected levels under provided camera parameters. (d) Simulated relationship between FAR and bowl fullness for the bowl in (b). (e) Projected ellipses corresponding to the rim of the bowl (red ellipse) and two flat food surfaces (blue ellipse and green ellipse)

Figure 3. (a) Example of a food image. (b) Segmented food surface (shaded region) and the extracted bowl rim (red ellipse). (c) Relationship between the FAR and the bowl fullness after cubic spline interpolation of precalculated points (red asterisks). The horizontal value of the blue asterisk in (c) represents the FAR of the food in (b). The vertical value provides the estimated bowl fullness F .

Figure 4. (a) The food is modeled as the sum of two parts separated by a flat circular surface (the shaded ellipse). (b) The height of the cone (marked as the red asterisk) is approximated using the intersected point of the food boundary and the projection of the central axis of the virtual 3D bowl. The lower end of the green line represents the center of the bowl bottom. (c) The food boundary and the contour of the model is best-matched by minimizing the squared error.

Figure 5. Three models representing bowls of different shapes. (a) $R = 60$ mm, $H = 48$ mm, $q = 6$. (b) $R = 100$ mm, $H = 30$ mm, $q = 4$. (c) $R = 100$ mm, $H = 80$ mm, $q = 20$.

Figure 6. The simulated FAR-F curves for the bowls in Fig. 5. Top row: The camera position is fixed while the view angle changes from 10° to 80° with an increment of 10° . Bottom row: The camera location and orientation are random.

Figure 7. Top row: picture of each bowl; Bottom row: estimated shape model for each bowl.

Figure 8. Three images of bowl #1 filled with black tea. The weight of this bowl is 217g, so the volumes of tea in these images are 25, 107, 219 ml respectively (the density of the black tea is approximated to be 1g/ml).

Figure 9. Simulated FAR- F curves for bowl #1 to bowl #3.

Figure 10. Comparison between estimated fullness and the ground truth for Bowl #1 to Bowl #3 (from top to bottom)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 11. Examples of food images

Figure 12. Box plots of bowl fullness errors for each food type. In each box, the red central line represents the median of the errors over all the food samples for the specific food type. The bottom and top edges of the box are the first and the third quartiles, respectively. The distance between these two edges is the interquartile range (IQR). The two whiskers are lines extending from the end of the IQR to the furthest error value within the whisker length (here the length equals to the IQR). Values that appear as a red + sign are outliers. Here an outlier is a value that is more than one time the IQR away from the bottom or top of the box.

Figure 13. Example images of lotus root. The manually chosen position of food peak point is marked as a red dot in each image.

Figure 14. Comparison of different estimation methods for images containing locus root.

Figure 15. Box plots of bowl fullness errors using the manual approach for food peak selection and the combined approach.